

Effect of Cognitive Restructuring Technique on Academic Task Procrastination of Secondary School Students in Onitsha Local Government Area of Anambra State

Prof. Christopher Amobi Nwankwo¹ & Egbunike, Nkechi Scholastica²

^{1&2}Department of Guidance and Counselling, Faculty of Education,
Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka

<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5105043>

Abstract

Procrastination is a behavioural problem that constitute a serious academic impediment to all human especially students and teachers in school environment. This study investigated the effect of cognitive restructuring technique on academic task procrastination among secondary school students in Onitsha North local government area of Anambra State. Three research questions and three null hypotheses raised and tested at 0.05 level of significance guided the study. Quasi experimental no-randomized pre- test and post-test, control group design was used for the study. Sample size of 580, SS 11 and J.SS 11 male and female secondary school students were purposively drawn from seven co-educational secondary schools with population size of 3550. The instrument for data collection was Tuckman procrastination Scale (TPS). Mean was used to answer the research Questions. ANCOVA was used in testing the null hypotheses. Findings of the study revealed among others that cognitive restructuring technique was effective in reducing academic task procrastination among secondary school students. The findings also showed that the different in the effects of cognitive restructuring technique on academic task procrastination of male and female secondary school students was significant. It was also found that the different in the effects of cognitive restructuring technique on academic task procrastination of junior and senior secondary school students was significant. The study recommended, among others that guidance counsellors should start early to adopt the use of cognitive restructuring technique in the reduction of academic task procrastination of secondary school students. Practicing counsellors should also make use of cognitive restructuring technique in counselling students towards reducing their academic task procrastination.

Key words: Effects, Cognitive restructuring, Technique, academic task, Procrastination

Introduction

Students have a lot of task to perform but for one reason or the other completing the task is often postponed so as to enjoy spare time and extracurricular activities which may lead to academic incompetence. These can be due to laziness, volume of work or because of other activities. In everyday life

students keep postponing task that they have to do, in order to improve their lives and become successful. Most times they do not manage their times well but use it wrongly by doing things that are not relevant to achieving academic and life goals and objectives, they tend to waste time on simply and pleasurable things against more important task and things that are hard to achieve, that will bring success and meaning to life. Most times this behaviour tends to make them, not to achieve important objectives and have regret afterwards. Generally postponing or delaying activities is called procrastination and when it has to do with delay in academic task, it is referred to as academic task procrastination.

Academic task procrastination is the act of needlessly delaying or postponing academic task to the point of experiencing subjective discomfort in an all too familiar problems. Ellis and Knaus (2014) described academic task procrastination as the desire to avoid an activity, the promise to do it later, and the use of excuse making to justify the delay and avoid blame. Ellis and Knaus estimated that about 95 percent of college students engage in academic task procrastination resulting in detrimental academic performance, including poor grades and course withdrawal. To Glick, Semb and Spencer (2015) academic task procrastination can come from measure of study habit such as last minute studying and attitude towards study.

Academic task Procrastination has been commonly understood as a maladaptive behaviour that tends to impede on successful academic experiences. Academic task procrastination as Eerde (2013) noted is linked with various adverse academic behaviours such as missing or late assignments, decreasing in task preparation time, and giving up studying. Academic task procrastination is a prevalent phenomenon especially among secondary school students due to the relatively flexible learning environment, and as some studies reported, that approximately 70 percent of secondary school students considered themselves procrastinators, and such reports cuts across the world (Argumedo, Diaz-Morales, Ferrari & O'Callaghan, 2017; Klassen, 2010; Seo, 2011).

Hopes, Burns, Hayes, Herbert and Winner (2010) revealed that academic task procrastination is related to poor academic performance Hopes, Burns, Hayes, Herbert and Winner have a conceptualization that procrastination is a phenomenon in which a person neglect to attend to a task or taken much time or delay in achieving a task. Sometimes, procrastination takes place until the "last minute" before a deadline. People may procrastinate personal issues (raising a stressful issue with a partner), health issues (seeing a doctor or dentist late), home care issues (patching a leak in a roof), or academic task/work obligations (completing a report or assignment).

Academic task procrastination can lead to feelings of guilt, inadequacy, depression, stress, self-doubt and failure in examination. A tendency to procrastinate is almost universal among secondary school students. When task and assignments are giving to students, many do not get around to signing up on time (Dennis, 2010). Sdorow (2017) noted that academic task procrastination can also be as a result of irrational cognition, evasiveness of task, low self-esteem, delayed study behaviour, time mismanagement, complex interaction of behaviour of cognition and affective component. The tendency to engage in all these maladaptive behaviour in school is called academic task procrastination. In school setting, the delay in performing activities is known as academic task procrastination, also when students do not do their academic work on time, it is also referred to academic task procrastination.

Academic task procrastination is a special form of procrastination that occurs in the academic settings. It involves knowing that one needs to carry out an academic task or undertake an academic activity, such as writing a term paper, studying for examinations, finishing a school related project, or undertaking the weekly reading assignments, but, for one reason or another, failing to motivate oneself to do so within the expected time frame (Ackerman & Gross, 2015). Although there is no universally accepted definition,

academic task procrastination can be defined as the postponement of academic task to the point where optimal performance becomes highly unlikely, resulting in a state of psychological distress (Ellis & Knaus, 2014; Ferrari, Johnson & McCown, 2016). Academic task procrastination may also be defined as any academic task that is delayed or avoided as a result of the discrepancy between intention and actual behaviour to the extent that it produces negative effect in the procrastinator. Academic task procrastination is considered to be a form of situational procrastination, which has been described as behaviour that is linked to a specific task (Harris & Sutton, 2015). Burka and Yuen (2015) noted that it is common for college students to delay academic tasks to the point of experiencing considerable anxiety and low grades.

Lay (2016) also conceived academic task procrastination as a frequent failure of doing academic works that ought to be done to reach goals. Someone who delays to complete his/her task without good reason is referred to a procrastinator, Noran (2010) therefore considered a procrastinator, as someone who knows what he/she is supposed to do and planning to perform the task, but does not complete the task, or excessively delays performing the task due to reason not sufficient enough for the delay, thus, working on less important obligation, rather than fulfilling the more important obligation, or he may use his or her time wastefully in some minor activities or pleasure.

Solomon, Rothblum and Murakami (2016) stated that high level of academic task procrastinations is associated with lower grades, and even when procrastination does not lead to failure, it can cause much suffering, because it put off work until the last minute, thereby making the procrastinator to work under pressure, skip classes, give false reasons for late work and feel ashamed of their last minute effort. Thus, Dennis (2010) noted that factors like evaluation anxiety, difficulties in making decision, rebellion against control, lack of assertion, perceived evasiveness of the task and overly performance standard about competency, influences academic task procrastination. Dennis, sees academic task procrastination as not meeting a dead line or failing to meet it. To Burka and Yuen (2015). For the purpose of this study academic task procrastination is the purposive delay, in the beginning and/or completion of an overt or covert act typically accomplished by subjective discomfort. It is to voluntarily delaying an intended course of action despite expecting to be worse off from the delay. Academic task procrastination has been a prevalent phenomenon in schools, college and university campuses for decades. In other not to procrastinate, students have to organize themselves through planning, acquire the right study habits, and restructure negative thinking patterns.

Curriculum experts and evaluators have expressed considerable concern over the deteriorating faulty thinking, wrong cognition of students and procrastination tendencies which affects student's academic performance in secondary schools. This could be attributed to students not being able to manage their time through cognitive oriented strategies. To complete academic task effectively, students needs a restructured cognition.

The term cognition refers to thoughts, and how they may be distorted that leads to develop inaccurate perceptions of what's going on in the world around. For example, many people experience anger or anxiety for no outwardly apparent reason, due to their own - perhaps distorted - impressions of events, for this reason cognitive theories are formulated towards exploring how humans acquire and process information and become knowledgeable about the world around them, they look for changes in cognitive processes from infancy through child hood and adolescent and into adulthood, they have been influential not only in helping people learn what to expect quantitatively from children, adolescent and adult various cognitive level, but also in helping people understand how to challenge and stimulate learning within human capability (Morgan, King, Weisz & Schopler, 2018). To address all this problems, humans need restructuring of their cognition.

Cognitive restructuring technique was developed by Aaron Beck (1963). It is an approach to the treatment of abnormal behaviour that tries to help individuals behave more adaptively by modifying their thoughts. Cognitive restructuring is a cover part of cognitive behavioural therapy (CBT) that refers to a number of different but related intervention techniques used to change behaviour and teaching individual to understand and modify thought and behaviour. Fincham, Foster and Hewstone (2015) defined cognitive-restructuring technique as a relatively short term treatment designed to get clients thinking about events in their lives in more rational and positive ways. According to Oguzie, Ani, Obi and Onyegirim (2018), cognitive restructuring is simply defined as a therapeutic process of learning to identify and dispute irrational or maladaptive thoughts. It is a psychotherapeutic process of learning to identify and dispute irrational or maladaptive thoughts known as cognitive distortions, such as all-or-nothing thinking (splitting), magical thinking, filtering, over-generalization, magnification, and emotional reasoning, which are commonly associated with many mental health disorders, (Abdullahi, Esere, Omotosho & Oniyanyi, 2011). In the context of this study, Cognitive restructuring technique is defined as a process of teaching students how to reduce negative reaction and thoughts by getting them to interpret situations or events and learning to replace negative thoughts with better and more beneficial thoughts.

To get the best out of our cognition we need cognitive restructuring (Dennis, 2010). Dennis continued that cognitive restructuring technique is the use of learning principles to change maladaptive thoughts, beliefs and feelings that underline emotional and behavioural problems. Cognitive restructuring technique is hence a cognitive-behavioural technique used to identify and correct negative thinking patterns. The technique involves altering negative automatic thoughts that occur in anxiety-provoking situations (such as "They think I'm boring") by replacing them with more rational beliefs (such as "I can't read other people's minds; they are probably just tired"). As thoughts are challenged and disputed, cognition is set right and the ability to elicit anxiety is weakened (Jees, John & Linda, 2017). Rohsenow and Smith (2007) outlined irrational and self-defeating beliefs that causes emotional upsets and maladaptive behaviour, such maladaptive behaviour or thought that all things must work perfectly well or that we must be loved by all has been criticized by Ellis who belief that many people would probably do well to give up irrational beliefs and self-defeating thoughts and rather improve self-acceptance and a better tolerance of daily annoyance will be benefits of cognitive restructuring (Ellis, 2006).

Corsini and Wedding (2015) noted that cognitive restructuring (CR) employs many strategies, such as Socratic questioning, thought recording and guided imagery and is used in many types of therapies, including cognitive behavioural therapy (CBT), and rational emotive therapy (RET). In other words, cognitive-restructuring therapists focus more on client's cognitive and affective experiences. A number of studies demonstrate considerable efficacy in using CR-based therapies to restructure cognition, save time and help students accomplish task for higher academic performance (Lewel, 2016; Oguzie, Ani, Obi & Onyegirim (2018).

According to Meichenbaum (1995), cognitive behaviour therapists strive to change misconceptions, strengthen coping skills, increase self-control and encourage self-reflection. Practically, during cognitive restructuring process, the primary objective of the therapist is to help clients to perceive environmental stimuli more accurately so that realistically dangerous situations are clearly differentiated from those where the source of harm is purely imaginary (Oguzie, Ani, Obi & Onyegirim, 2018). The emphasis is on the effect of thought on behaviour and behavioural change techniques. By so doing, clients are placed in a better position to gain more understanding of themselves and their environment so as to turn around their maladaptive thinking pattern. Cognitive restructuring technique offers hope because it shows how wrong thinking and behaviour can be unlearned, it also shows how more effective ways of thinking and behaviour can be learned.

Despite numerous effort made by the previous researchers in finding a lasting solution to the problem of academic task procrastination, among secondary school students, the problems no doubts still posed serious challenges to guidance counsellors, teachers and other professionals in seeing that an effective solution to the problem be realized since it affects both male and females. Gender based studies on academic task procrastination demonstrated that female students procrastinate more frequently in their academic task (Rodarte – Luna & Sherry, 2017) while some studies proved a different attitude depicting that academic task procrastination is common among male students (Arif, Muneer, Noor & Khan, 2016; Balkis & Duru, 2016). Findings of the study showed that males are more intended to procrastinate in academic task than females. On the other hand, another group of studies reported that gender has no effect on the academic task procrastination behaviour (Okun, 2011). Ferrari and Ozer (2011) in that regard found no significant difference between male and female students on academic task procrastination, to control and manage academic task procrastination, students must learn to restructure their cognition and manage their time effectively.

To achieve reduction or curtail the problem of students academic task procrastination something need to be done. It is on this note that the researchers deemed it necessary to fill the existing gap by embarking on this study with the hope that treating students with cognitive restructuring technique will help them restructure their cognition, thoughts, plan their time and organize their life in general to stop academic task procrastination for a better academic performance and successful future.

Research Questions

This study was guided by the following research questions:

1. What is the effect of cognitive restructuring technique on academic task procrastination of secondary school students when compared with those treated with conventional counselling using their pre-test and post-test scores?
2. What is the difference in the effects of cognitive restructuring technique on academic task procrastination of male and female secondary school students using their pre-test and post-test scores?
3. What is the difference in the effects of cognitive restructuring technique on academic task procrastination of Junior and senior secondary school students using their pre-test and post-test scores?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant difference in the effect of cognitive restructuring technique on academic task procrastination among secondary school students when compared with conventional counselling using their pre-test and post-test scores.
2. There is no significant difference in the effects of cognitive restructuring technique on academic task procrastination among male and female secondary school students using their pre-test and post-test scores.
3. There is no significant difference in the effects of cognitive restructuring technique on academic task procrastination among junior and senior secondary school students using their pre-test and post-test scores?

Method

This study adopted the quasi-experimental pre-test and post-test control group design. Quasi-experiment is a type of study that seeks to determine the effect of a treatment paradigm on a non-randomised sample. According to Asgari and Nunes (2011), such study is conducted in a natural setting rather than laboratory conditions, but in this design, variables are isolated, controlled and manipulated. The study was conducted in Onitsha North local government area of Anambra State. The population of this study was 3550 respondents made up of male and female students from all coeducational secondary schools in Onitsha North Local Government area of Anambra State, identified with academic task procrastination problems. The sample size for the study was 580 male and female students in JS 11 and SS 11. The instrument that was used for assessment is Tuckman Procrastination Scale (TPS) developed in 1991. The instrument is self-report instrument which identifies academic procrastinators, through measuring of procrastination tendencies. The Procrastination Scale (PS) consists of 16-items which are scored on a four-point Likert scale (i.e. 1 = that's me for sure, 2 = that's my tendency, 3 = that's not my tendency, 4 = that's not me for sure). The Tuckman Procrastination Scale is a standardised, with internal consistency reliability estimate of 0.82.

Each participant in their individual classes in their respective schools was given the instrument to respond to the items. All responses were scored according to the specification on the Tuckman procrastination scale manual. The data relating to the research questions were analysed using the mean, while data relating to the null hypotheses were analysed using the Analysis of Co-variance (ANCOVA).

Results:

Table 1: Pretest and Posttest academic task procrastination mean scores of students treated with cognitive restructuring technique and those treated with conventional counselling (Norm = 40)

Source of Variation	N	Pretest Mean	Posttest Mean	Lost Mean	Remark
CR-Tech.	199	59.67	29.67	30.00	Effective
Conventional Counselling	188	55.21	43.85	11.36	

In table 1, it was observed that the students treated with cognitive restructuring technique had pretest mean score of 59.67 and posttest mean score of 29.67 with lost mean 30.00 in their academic task procrastination, while those in the control group who received conventional counselling had pretest mean score of 55.21 and posttest mean score of 43.85 with lost mean 11.36. With posttest mean score of 29.67 which is below the norm of 40.00 cognitive restructuring technique is effective in reducing academic task procrastination among secondary school students.

Table 2: Pretest and Posttest academic task procrastination mean scores among male and female students treated with cognitive restructuring technique

Source of Variation	N	Pretest Mean	Posttest Mean	Lost Mean	Remark
Male	95	59.06	28.03	31.03	More Effective
Female	104	60.23	31.16	29.07	

In table 2, it was observed that male students treated with cognitive restructuring technique had pretest mean score of 59.06 and posttest mean score of 31.03 with lost mean 31.03 in their academic task procrastination, while the female students treated with the technique had pretest mean score of 60.23 and posttest mean score of 31.16 with lost mean 29.07. With lost mean of 31.03 as against 29.07 for male and female students respectively, cognitive restructuring technique is more effective in reducing academic task procrastination among male secondary school students.

Table 3: Pretest and Posttest academic task procrastination mean scores among junior and senior students treated with cognitive restructuring technique.

Source of Variation	N	Pretest Mean	Posttest Mean	Lost Mean	Remark
Junior	98	60.00	32.78	27.20	
Senior	101	59.36	26.65	32.71	More effective

Table 3 reveals that junior students treated with cognitive restructuring technique had pretest mean score of 60.00 and posttest mean score of 32.78 with lost mean 27.20 in their academic task procrastination, while the senior students treated with the technique had pretest mean score of 59.36 and posttest mean score of 26.65 with lost mean 32.71. With lost mean of 27.20 for junior as against 32.71 for senior students, cognitive restructuring technique is more effective in reducing academic task procrastination among senior secondary school students than their junior counterparts.

Table 4: ANCOVA on the effect of cognitive restructuring technique on academic task procrastination among secondary school students when compared with those who received conventional counselling

Source of variation	SS	df	MS	Cal. F	Pvalue	P ≤ 0.05
Corrected Model	19492.212	2	9746.106			
Intercept	1317.020	1	1317.020			
PRETEST	46.711	1	46.711			
METHODS	14547.331	1	14547.331	320.433	.000	S
Error	17433.230	384	45.399			
Total	554150.000	387				
Corrected Total	36925.442	386				

Table 4 indicates that at 0.05 level of significance, 1df numerator and 386df denominator, the calculated F is 320.43 with Pvalue of 0.00 which is less than 0.05. Therefore, the first null hypothesis is rejected. So, the effect of cognitive restructuring technique on the academic task procrastination among secondary school students is significant.

Table 5: ANCOVA on the effects of cognitive restructuring technique on academic task procrastination of male and female secondary school students

Source of variation	SS	df	MS	Cal. F	Pvalue	P ≤ 0.05
Corrected Model	2282.157	4	570.539			
Intercept	170.673	1	170.673			
PRETEST	109.035	1	109.035			
GENDER	37.942	1	237.942	5.774	.017	S
Error	7993.954	194	41.206			
Total	185438.000	199				
Corrected Total	10276.111	198				

Table 5 reveals that at 0.05 level of significance, 1df numerator and 198df denominator, the calculated F is 5.77 with Pvalue of 0.017 which is less than 0.05. Therefore, the fourth null hypothesis is rejected. So, the effects of cognitive restructuring technique on academic task procrastination among male and female secondary school students differ significantly.

Table 6: ANCOVA on the effects of cognitive restructuring technique on academic task procrastination among junior and senior secondary school students

Source of variation	SS	df	MS	Cal. F	Pvalue	P ≤ 0.05
Corrected Model	7292.817	2	3646.408			
Intercept	170.908	1	444.908			
PRETEST	3.926	1	3.926			
CLASSLEVEL	1565.858	1	1565.858	38.001	0.00	S
Error	7993.954	194	41.206			
Total	185438.000	199				
Corrected Total	10276.111	198				

Table 6 shows that at 0.05 level of significance, 1df numerator and 198df denominator, the calculated F 38.0046 with Pvalue of 0.00 which is less than 0.05. Therefore, the sixth null hypothesis is rejected. Hence, the effects of cognitive restructuring technique on academic task procrastination among junior and senior secondary school students differ significantly.

Discussion

The findings of this study revealed that cognitive restructuring technique was effective in reducing academic task procrastination of secondary school students. The findings also revealed that the effect of cognitive restructuring technique on the academic task procrastination of secondary school students was significant. Through cognitive restructuring technique the students were able to restructure their cognition, and were able to modify their procrastination behaviour. This means that those students treated with cognitive restructuring technique recorded great improvement in reducing their academic task procrastination. This finding agrees with the report from the study by Oguzie, Ani, Obi and Onyegirim (2018) who observed that cognitive restructuring was significantly effective in reducing maladaptive behaviour among secondary school students. The result also corresponds with the findings of Beck (2015) who agreed that cognitive restructuring technique empowered students to restructure the mental mistake they make that leads to problems of academic task procrastination.

The effectiveness of cognitive restructuring technique in this study could be explained by the cognitive theory which states that distorted or dysfunctional thinking underlines all psychological disturbances, which also affect, moulds beliefs and behaviour. The key idea of the theory is that not events themselves that affect our behaviour but how we perceive the events. The fundamental belief impacts on our thoughts in any given situation and that different people or students have different reactions to the same situation and that the degree of negative thought determines the severity of the attack they launch, resulting in error in logic and or faulty information processing. Cognitive restructuring thus helps students to restructure their faulty cognition and faulty thought patterns so as to be able to interpret events with greater accuracy. Human beings are rational and irrational, the irrationality in man sometimes creates problems for them while the rational helps them look at the problem rationally and proffer solutions, to reduce their academic task procrastination, and help them achieve more in life and become acceptable members of the society. The result of the findings is consistent with the study of (Adesu, 2016; Ahmed, 2016) whose studies on the effect of cognitive restructuring was significant in reduction of conduct disorder among adolescents.

Results of the study show that the effects of cognitive restructuring technique on academic task procrastination among male and female secondary school students differ significantly. The findings show that the male students' academic task procrastination reduced more than the female students, indicating that the male students have a higher rate of reduction in their academic task procrastination than the female students, this may be that the male students exhibit special interest in the treatment hence more reduction in their academic task procrastination. This finding is in consonance with the reports of previous researchers

(Oguzie, Ani, Obi & Onyegirim, 2018; Feldman, 2019) who found that there is significant gender difference in the effect of cognitive restructuring technique in reducing maladaptive behaviours. The findings also disagree with Ahmed (2016) who indicated that gender was not a significant factor among students exposed to cognitive restructuring on reduction of phobia among secondary school students.

This present study is in consonance with the results of Hermaous (2017), who declare that cognitive restructuring was effective in self-esteem among the members of the study due to gender. The present study is also in line with Sirious (2018) whose results showed statistically significant difference at ($\alpha > 0.05$) in favour of male on cognitive restructuring technique. Pychyl (2017) reported that both male and female students have similar levels of reduction in their academic task procrastination but the gender gap emerged and boys are reported to have a higher reduction. Cognitive restructuring technique enables students to acquire new cognition through provision of adequate information and considerable practice offered by the professional.

Another finding of this study shows that there was significant difference in the effects of cognitive restructuring technique on the junior and senior secondary school students' academic task procrastination. The finding also showed that the senior students who participated in the cognitive restructuring treatment benefited more than their junior counterparts. This finding supported previous report in literature by Nnodum (2014) and Ahmed (2016) who reported that older students benefited more from cognitive restructuring technique than the younger ones. The finding of the study equally agrees with (Nwokolo, Anyamene & Nzerem, 2020; Oguzie, Ani, Obi & Onyegirim, 2018) whose findings showed that cognitive restructuring technique proved more successful in reducing undesirable behaviour among senior students.

The reason for this finding of the study could be attributed to the notion that older an individual the higher their level thinking faculty. Possibly, the senior students benefited more from the cognitive restructuring treatment because they have higher reasoning capacity and perhaps were able to change their thought pattern faster due to their older age. However, the study contradicts the findings of previous researchers (Abodike, 2010; Saputra, 2017) who reported that there was no significant difference in the effects of cognitive restructuring technique in reducing undesirable behaviour among younger and older secondary school students. The possible reason for the contradiction between the findings of the above mentioned researchers and that of this study may be as a result difference in methodology, location or human error at the course of their researches.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of this study, it was concluded that cognitive restructuring technique had significant effect on the reduction of academic task procrastination of secondary school students. It was also concluded that cognitive restructuring technique was more effective among the male and senior students than their female and junior counterparts, respectively.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study and the educational implications of the present study are listed, the following recommendations are hereby made:

1. Counsellors should employ cognitive restructuring technique in the reduction of students' academic task procrastination of secondary school students irrespective of gender.
2. Students, especially those with high academic task procrastination and faulty thinking should be exposed to appropriate technique like cognitive restructuring technique by the school counsellors, as this will help them to improve their thinking and reduce their academic task procrastination.
3. School administrator need to work towards organizing training programmes for guidance counsellor in schools on cognitive restructuring for their effective use in other to reduce the spirally accelerated effects of academic task procrastination among secondary school students.

References

- Abdullahi, R. P., Esere, H. G. A., Omotosho, V.C. & Oniyangu, C (2011). *Know your limit then ignore them*. Florida: Bridge Publishing Inc.
- Abodike, E .A. (2010). *Behaviour modification: Principles and practice*. Ibadan: Babs Obitunji Publishing.
- Ackerman, C. & Gross, P. (2015). *The effect of psychotherapy*. Baltimore: William & Wilkins.
- Ahmed, M. S. (2016). Effects of cognitive restructuring and graded exposure counseling techniques on school phobia among secondary school students in Kaduna Metropolis, Nigeria. *Unpublished masters thesis, University of Illorin*.
- Argumedo, C., Diaz, M., Ferrari, B. & O-Callaghan, B. (2017). *Principles of modification*. New York: Holt Richard and Wiston.
- Arif, A., Muneur, P., Khan, K. & Noor, J. (2016). *The 7 Secrets of the Prolific: The Definitive Guide to Overcoming Procrastination, Perfectionism, and Writer's Block*, New York: Adam Media.
- Asgari, V. & Nunes, P. (2011). *Experimental and quasi experimental research in technology system*. Sheffield: University of Sheffield Pub.
- Balkis, M. & Duru, E. (2016). Prevalence of academic procrastination behaviour among pre-service teachers and its relationship with demographic and individual preference. *Journal of Theory and Practice in Education*. 5 (1), 18 – 32.
- Beck, A. (1963). Automatic thoughts and cognitive restructuring in cognitive behavioural group therapy for social anxiety disorder. *Cognitive Therapy Research*. 34: 1–12.
- Beck, A. T. (2015). *Love is never enough*. New York: Harper & Row.
- Burka, J. B. & Yuen, L. M. (2015). *Procrastination*. Menlo Park C.A: Addison-Wesley.
- Cosine, B. & Wedding, P. (2015). Different Cultures See Deadlines Differently. *Harvard Business Review*. Retrieved 2018-12-04.
- Dennis, B. C. (2010). *Advanced Placement Examination in Psychology*. New Jersey: Realist Press.
- Eerde, V. (2013). Procrastination by pigeons: preference for larger, more delayed work requirements. *Journal of the Experimental Analysis of Behaviour*. 65 (1): 159–171.
- Ellis, A. & Knaus, W. H. (2014). How Different Cultures Understand Time". *Business Insider*. Retrieved 2018-12-04.
- Ellis, A. (2006). *Reason and emotion in psychology*. New York, Lyle Stuart
- Feldman, V. (2019). *Assumptions on how to restructure cognition*. New York, Eddison.
- Ferrari, J. J. & Ozer, B. U. (2011). Delaying disposing and Examination of the relationship between procrastination and cluster across generations current psychology. *New Brunswick, N. J* (1046 - 1310) 37 (2).
- Ferrari, J. J., Johnson, J. & Mc Crown, H. (2016). *A textbook of psychology, (2nd ed)*. Philadelphia: Saunders.

- Ficham, B., Foster, V. & Hewstone, C. (2015). The role of conscientiousness as a mediator in the relationship of academic procrastination and perceived social loafing. *North American Journal of Psychology* 14(1), 13 – 24.
- Glick, C., Semb, B. & Spencer, V. (2015). *The Psychologist*. Madison: Brown and Benchmark Pub.
- Harris, B. & Sulton, V. (2015). *Understanding Psychology* (2nd ed). London. McGraw Hill.College Press.
- Hermans, M. G. (2017). Electro convulsive therapy: A review comprehensive. *Psychiatry* 15, 304 – 314.
- Hope, P., Burns, D. D., Hayes, J. R., Herbert, W., & Warner, S. (2010). Cognitive restructuring exceptional memory. *American Scientist* 70, 607-615.
- Jees, B., John, P. & Linda, J. (2017). Driven To Distraction: Recognizing and Coping with Attention Deficit Disorder from Childhood Through Adulthood. *Touchstone*. Retrieved 2013-07-30.
- Klassen, R. M. (2010). *The now habit: A strategic program for overcoming procrastination and enjoying guilt-free play*. New York: Penguin.
- Meichenbaum, D. A. (1995). *Thoughts and feelings; taking control of your moods and your life*. Oakland New Harbinger.
- Morgan, V., King, B., Weisz, W. & Schopler, C. (2018). *Time management from inside out: the foolproof system for taking control of your schedule and your life* (2nd ed). New York: Henry holt owl. 285.
- Nnodum, B. (2014). *Current trends in Cognitive Restructuring*. Pittsburgh: University of Pittsburgh.
- Noran, D. C. (2010). A closer look at the relationships among trait procrastination, neuroticism, and conscientiousness. *Personality and Individual Differences*. 40: 27–37.
- Nwokolo, C., Anyamene, A. & Nzerem, H. (2020). Relative effectiveness of cognitive restructuring and contingency contracting techniques on bullying behaviour among secondary school students in Imo state. *Journal of Guidance and Counselling Studies*, 4(1),123-134
- Oguzie, A.E., Ani, D.P., Obi, B.A. & Onyegirim B.O. (2018). Effect of cognitive restructuring technique on fear tendency among secondary school students in Owerri Municipal Council of Imo state. *International Journal of Advanced Research and Publications*, 2(1), 34-38.
- Okwum, M. (2011). *26 words that can change your life: Nurture your mind, heart and soul to transform your life and relationships*; 76–100.
- Rodate-Luna, B. & Sherry, A. (2017). Gender based Procrastination, Impulsivity, and Goal-Management Ability Implications for the Evolutionary Origin of Procrastination. *Psychological Science*. 25 (6): 1178–88.
- Rohsenow, B. & Smith, C. (2007). *A Guide to the Project Management Body of Knowledge (PMBOK Guide)*.ISBN 1-930699-45-X.Archived from the original on 2008-11-04.
- Saputra, W. N. (2017). Effectiveness of cognitive restructuring technique to reduce academic procrastination of vocational high school students. *International Journal of Counseling and Education*, 2(1): pp. 6-10.
- Sdorow, L. W. (2017). Procrastination and Personality, Performance and Mood. *Personality and Individual Differences*;30: 95–106.
- Seo, V.O. (2011). *A handbook of cognitive restructuring*. Lagos, Babs Olutunji Publisher

- Sirois, F. (2018). I'll look after my health later. A replication and extension of the procrastination health model with community dwelling adults. *Journal of Personality and Individual Differences*, 43(1), 15-26.
- Solomon, L. J., Rothblum, V. & Murakani, N. (2016). *Academic procrastination: cognitive-behavioural correlates*. (pdf).archived (pdf) from the original on 2016-07-29. Statistics perspective of male middle school male students. *International Journal of Humanities and Cultural Studies*, 2464 – 2487. Retrieved from <https://www.ijhcs.com/index.php/>